

IMPREGNATION OF BLEACHED JUTE YARNS WITH SYNTHETIC RESINS. PART II. EFFECT OF PRETREATMENTS AND BLEACHING PROCESSES ON THE WET-STRENGTH OF RESIN-TREATED YARNS

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It has been found that the level of lignin content regulates the improvement of wet-strength, other conditions remaining the same. The lower the lignin content of the bleached yarns, the better is the improvement obtained on impregnation with resins. If the lignin content falls too low, the yarns disintegrate in contact with water, thereby making the use of aqueous solutions of resins impossible. Chlorite bleaching gives a better improvement of wet-strength after resin treatment than sodium hypochlorite or bleaching powder, due to hemicelluloses remaining more or less in tact. Pretreatment of yarns with 2% sodium carbonate or with rectified spirit containing 2% pyridine gives satisfactory improvements.

It is well known that the binding materials which determine the strength of the jute fibre consist of hemicelluloses and lignin¹⁻³. Bleaching processes generally remove lignin with or without any appreciable effect on hemicelluloses³⁻⁵. As more and more lignin is removed, more carboxyl groups are found in the bleached jute. These carboxyl groups are in a position to attract basic resins like melamine and urea-formaldehyde, resulting in an appreciable improvement of wet-strength. In the following investigations, bleaching powder and sodium chlorite have been used as bleaching agents. The latter reagent obtains better improvement as its effect on the hemicelluloses is insignificant. On account of the cost of this process we have, however, given more emphasis on bleaching powder.

Bleaching operations are generally facilitated by treatment of jute with dilute alkali⁶. For this purpose we have used a 2% solution of sodium carbonate and pyridinated (2%) alcohol. It is interesting to note that extraction of jute with pyridinated alcohol gave a green chlorophyll-like product, and the bleached yarns maintained a whiteness which did not tarnish on keeping for a fairly long time.

It is proposed to study the effect of pretreatments with dilute alkali and alcoholic pyridine and of the action of the two bleaching agents on the wet-strength of resin-impregnated yarns. The extent of bleaching is generally reflected on the lignin content. The lower the lignin content, the greater is the improvement of wet-strength obtained after resination of yarns. If,

however, the bleaching is carried too far so as to reduce the lignin content below 2% or so, the fibres cannot be handled in the moist state as they easily fall into pulp in contact with water.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bleaching powder process.—Bleaching powder (available chlorine, 25-26%) (12 g.) was mixed with water (700 ml.) and thoroughly stirred. Sodium carbonate (10 g.) was then added, the sludge allowed to settle and the clear supernatant liquid drained off. Equal lengths of yarns (wt. 24 to 25 g.), carefully fastened at two ends, were soaked in water, squeezed and then treated with the hypochlorite solution (liquor ratio, 1 : 25) for 3 hours at room temperature (25°-26°). The yarns were washed and antichlored with 6 g. sodium hydrosulphite for 1 hour at room temperature (liq. ratio, 1 : 25). This operation was repeated for a second time in two-stage bleaching and the yarns were washed, air-dried, conditioned and analysed for lignin content by the method of Norman and Jenkins⁷.

Sodium chlorite process.—The yarns (20-25 g.) were treated with a solution composed of 30 g. of sodium chlorite, 9 g. of sodium acetate and 29 ml. of glacial acetic acid in 1 litre of water. The pH was maintained at 4.5-5.0, liquor ratio 1 : 60 and temperature 60°-70° for 4 hours during which time the yarns were occasionally stirred. The bleached yarns were then thoroughly washed, antichlored with 0.2% sodium hydrosulphite for about 20 minutes using a liquor ratio 1 : 25, and again washed with water. The yarns were again bleached (two stage) and antichlored as above when a low lignin content was desired.

Pretreatment with sodium carbonate.—This consisted in warming 20-25 g. of the material with 2% sodium carbonate solution at liquor ratio 1 : 25 for 2 hours at 60°-70°. It was then thoroughly washed and bleached by either of the two processes described above.

Pretreatment with pyridinated rectified spirit.—The yarns (20-25 g.) were refluxed in a Soxhlet with rectified spirit containing 2% pyridine for about 4 hours. The yarns were then pressed in a Büchner and finally washed with excess water. The alcoholic solution on evaporation gave a greenish waxy product which responded to tests for chlorophyll.

The various samples, as obtained above, were treated with resin solutions, squeezed, baked with curing agents, as described before, and tested for wet-strength on a standard Goodbrand Single Thread Tester after soaking the yarns in water for 45 minutes and keeping them wet during testing at 26.6°. The average value of 30 tests with 18 inches grip length was taken for calculating the quality ratio (Q.R.) (cf. Part I⁹).

With the fall of the lignin content, the Q. R. of the bleached yarns also falls. This loss of Q. R. in relation to the Q. R. of the original unbleached yarns is shown in Table I. This table also indicates the relative improvement of M. F. resinated yarns with varying percentage of residual lignin content.

TABLE I
Effect of removal of lignin on quality ratio and wet-strength of bleached yarns
impregnated with 4.5% M. F.

Pretreatment.	Bleaching agent.	Residual lignin content.	Loss of Q. R.	Improvement.
Nil	Sodium chlorite*	1.08%	84.25%	62.9%
"	"	1.33	80.44	60.1
"	"	1.40	78.60	56.3
Spirit + 2% pyridine	Bleaching powder**	2.88	74.71	55.7
"	"	3.14	73.22	54.0
"	"	3.45	71.79	50.6
"	Bleaching powder†	4.38	70.00	43.8
"	"	4.52	63.30	41.5
Sodium carbonate	"	4.80	57.13	38.1
"	"	5.10	55.50	33.3
Nil	"	5.74	50.57	27.6
"	"	6.20	48.35	22.0
"	Sodium hypochlorite‡	9.56	42.10	9.2
"	Sodium hypochlorite††	11.31	26.31	1.2

*Bleached in two stages.

**Bleached in three stages with available chlorine conc. of 5 g./litre and 3 g./litre (twice).

†Bleached in two stages with available chlorine conc. of 5 g./litre and 3 g./litre.

‡Bleached in two stages with available chlorine conc. of 3 g./litre and 4 g./litre.

††Bleached in one stage with available chlorine conc. of 3 g./litre.

Pretreatment with sodium carbonate improved colour and softness of the bleached yarns. In the case of pyridinated rectified spirit, the improvement of colour was more marked. In the latter case, the finished material was feathery white and no appreciable deterioration of colour was observed within six months.

In the case of bleaching operation with hypochlorites, alkaline conditions were maintained. If the solution were made acidic, chlorination of lignin and oxidation of hemicelluloses would have taken place. The fibre quality therefore deteriorated to a great extent. For that reason a pH 9.0-11.5, as recommended by Ridge and co-workers³⁻⁵, was used. In order to maintain the pH on the alkaline side, addition of sodium carbonate (10 g./litre) was used.

Table I shows that the greater the removal of lignin, the greater is the loss of tensile strength of jute yarns. This variation is, however, not regular. The relative improvement of wet-strength by resin treatment was

greater in the case of low-lignin samples. The bleached yarns with a lignin content of 1-3% imparted improvement in wet-strength ranging from 62 to 54%. In the case of yarns containing 3-4.5% lignin, the improvements varied from 54 to 40%. Those containing 4.5 to 5.5% lignin showed improvements to the extent of 40-30%. With higher contents of lignin, improvements of the order of 20-30% were obtained, though in some cases it was less than 10%.

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R E F E R E N C E S

1. Chowdhury *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 239.
2. Sarkar *et al.*, *J. Text. Inst.*, 1948, 39, T 1.
3. Ridge & Little, *ibid.*, 1942, 33, T 33.
4. Ridge & Little, *ibid.*, 1944, 35, T 21.
5. Ridge, Little & Wharton, *ibid.*, 1944, 35, T 93.
6. Macmillan, Sengupta & Maumdar, *this Journal*, 1949, 12, 105.
7. Norman & Jenkins *Biochem. J.*, 1935, 29, 2147.
8. Chatterjee *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1954, 17, 155.